

D5.3 Leadership and Decision-Making Action Plan

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-ROLES tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
Task 5.3	

GEARING-ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

BAME	Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GEPI	Gender Equality Plan Implementer
RFO	Research Funding Organization
WLB	Work-life balance
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document is the Leadership and Decision-Making Action Plan (D5.3) developed under task 5.3 by WP5 leader UDEUSTO. The aim of the report is to first analyze the main gaps in terms of leadership on each institution and, second, provide recommendations that can be incorporated into GEPs by implementing partners. Two common actions at a consortium level have been identified, as well as specific need for the different partners. For each of the activities, some of the existing tools or instruments identified under D5.1 have been mentioned for inspiration.

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1. Introduction

Within the framework of the GEARING-Roles project, one of the specific aims is the analysis of the leadership and decision-making processes from a gender perspective as well as the proposition of recommendations for their improvement.

This document is intended to give some recommendations to be incorporated into the GEPs, particularly to the leadership and decision-making section, which are being designed by each GEP implementing partner.

The methodology that has been followed to produce these recommendations consisted on a two-sided process:

On one hand, the context of the GEP implementers has been assessed in order to set the starting point, based on available information from each institution. This process consisted on a first reading of the Institutional Assessment Report provided by the institutions, which contains both quantitative and qualitative information. Then, in order to go deeper into the leadership and decision-making area, a qualitative analysis of the interviews carried out with individuals at leadership positions on each GEP implementer has been performed. In order to set a common framework for these qualitative analysis, WP coordinators (UDEUSTO) developed categories of analysis based on the most relevant dimensions covered in the interviews, which were then shared with all GEPs, as well as a common structure and guidelines for the analysis. Due to data protection and privacy issues, a common framework was developed by UDEUSTO that allow partners to self-assess their interviews. Then, once all the reports were anonymized, UDEUSTO extracted common issues and dissimilarities across partners in order to get a picture not only at an individual level, but also as a consortium.

On the other hand, in parallel, a desk research has been conducted to identify inspiring practices (see D5.1). This allowed the WP5 team to select the most interesting initiatives which we believe would most effectively address the different challenges identified in the Institutional Assessments, in order to present them as recommendations for GEPs.

The present document is divided into two main sections. In the first one, the main issues arising from the leadership sections of the Institutional Assessment Reports and the qualitative analysis of the interviews are presented. Then, in the second section, inspired by the desk research of practices developed, we propose recommendations specifically for each of the GEP implementing partners, with the aim of reducing the main challenges that each of them is facing in this field. Furthermore, some actions at the consortium level are also recommended, targeting to some common elements shared by all GEPs which could be addressed in a better way through the exchange of experiences between consortium partners.

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2. Issues arising from Institutional Assessment Reports

This section contains a summary of the different issues each GEP implementing institution has identified on their Institutional Assessment Reports. The information provided shows that most of the institutions have common challenges in leadership, with small variations due to several factors, such as the national context and the performance of the institution regarding gender equality.

2.1. IGOT

First off, it is important to highlight how statistics on IGOT's Assessment Report show that there are gender imbalances in representation at Faculty level: The three main bodies at IGOT (management council, scientific council and pedagogic council) are men-dominated, with a very low women participation rate.

From the qualitative information it can be concluded that, although participants showed different degrees of perception regarding gender inequalities underpinning the academic life of IGOT, both interviews presented a common storyline: an initial position of denial of an existing gender issue followed by a change of opinion after confrontation with extensive data from the gender audit. Recognition of existing inequalities is fundamental, and the availability of data, on the national and institutional level, had a great impact in prompting participants to provide explanations for those discrepancies.

With regards to gender inequalities in terms of access to leadership positions and decision-making bodies, the interviewees state that there is an institutional culture where competence is valued above all else. In any case, IGOT is a small school of the University of Lisbon and a number of its decision-making bodies require members to be full professors (or equivalent) in order to participate. As there are not many full professors, and even fewer female full professors, there is not much room for manoeuvre.

By referring to structural resistances and obstacles to a more inclusive gender policy at IGOT, the contradictions of 'politically correctness' (being in favour of gender equality in theory but not in practice) are highlighted. On a different note, the imbalance between men and women at IGOT are seen as a reflection of wider social inequalities. The self-interrogation 'What can we do?' works somehow as a waiver of liability, inasmuch as local inequalities reflect wider societal differences, from which the institute cannot escape.

Another aspect that has been identified, mainly in the qualitative data, is the fact that management positions have been offered to woman, but they declined enrolling in leadership tasks.

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Finally, another issue identified at the IGOT analysis is the lack of awareness about the existence of a gender-related problem at management bodies, which have been expressed precisely by some components of the management bodies. Nevertheless, it is also recognized that there is a clear tendency to occupy the management positions with men (bias), but no specific justification is given. Wording is very telling and can expose deep-seated assumptions that might come to surface (or that are already very evident): expressions such as ‘tend’/‘tendency’, ‘[the numbers] are what they are’, or ‘we still have a traditional inheritance from our country’ often reveal arguments that have been naturalized by participants, which have to do with the roles, skills and capabilities relating to women and to men.

2.2. UL

As in the case of IGOT, Faculty of Arts of University of Ljubljana faces gender imbalances at both University and Faculty level. In this case, the disequilibrium in the top management at Faculty level is clear: in the 2009-2019 period, there have been thirteen male vice-deans versus only five women. At middle management positions, in contrast, there is gender balance, even with more women than men in most of the positions.

Apart from the quantitative data showed above, the qualitative information reveals a tension between gender equality and academic achievements, understanding the relationship between them as mutually exclusive.

The overall impression is that the interviewees have basic understanding of and are in principle in favour of gender equality. They also see some areas for intervention, such as progression in academic titles, work life balance, gender sensitive language or the need for sex disaggregated data. They also expressed a certain level of sensitivity towards gender equality, but interviews also reveal the need for further gender awareness raising activities.

In general, none of the interviewees sees objective, structural conditions in accessing leadership positions as a challenge to gender equality. Although some of them identified institutional resistances, they expressed support for gender equality and recognised the potential for change they have as a person in leadership position.

Nevertheless, resistances, in form of scepticism, but mostly on account of the lack of knowledge on the matter, were expressed while discussing possible equality mechanisms for assuring gender equality in leadership positions, such as quotas. According to interviewees such mechanisms (beyond the issues of equality in leadership) are still perceived as unjust, even by the women themselves, – due to favouring women on account of lowering the standards/criteria.

Leadership positions are seen as demanding due to increased inability to balance work and non-work related activities, and also due to pursuing academic careers in parallel. Most of the

interviewees at least partially understand their personal productivity in terms of masculine perception and recognise the burden of balancing family and private life with the demands of the job – as part of structural conditions.

On the other hand, a presence of solidarity and collaboration is detected, which in individual professional practices deviate from standard each-for-himself individualism, stemming from masculine codes traditionally inscribed in the structure of academic institutions.

Finally, regarding decision-making processes, the size of the faculty and the specificities of the leadership and related processes, is seen as a factor adding more complexity to the procedures (i.e. there are less options when selecting candidates) and, as a consequence, to the achievement of a gender balance.

2.3. OBU

Data reported in the Institutional Report show that women are generally well represented across all committees and decision-making groups, and this reflects a university commitment to diversity of representation. However, there is less consistency in visible ethnic diversity and representation of self-identified BAME (Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic) staff. This is being monitored to help identify gaps and drive change. As committee memberships are drawn from existing leadership and management positions, their composition tends to reproduce the profile of the prevailing university hierarchy which may take some time to change.

Being part of, contributing to and having responsibilities at a committee or sub-committee were identified as important channels that one can embark on to progress to leadership roles and responsibilities. It was felt that opportunities to shadow existing committee members and deputising would allow for more committee participation for women and also BAME staff, increasing their participation.

A good practice was identified in terms of the diversity of the groups that formally contribute to decision-making: Structures where an LGBTQ+ planning group (which includes representation from the university HR function as well as from different groups such as BAME) is consulted on changes to university internal structures and processes. This allows for some consideration of staff and student needs arising from a range of characteristics, in addition to gender.

With regard to qualitative information, there is a concern about whether we are facing gendered patterns of inclusion when appointing new leaders. There is a risk of assigning roles in softer areas to women (HR, Students experience, Staff Experience). On its side, profiles in top positions come from a more scientific background instead that being people with a cultural studies background, with the risk of not understanding the language of addressing gender inequality.

Several interviewees argued that issues remain for BAME staff, particularly BAME women. This perceived lack of BAME individuals at senior levels is supported by statistical evidence outlined

in the institutional report. There are also perceptions that there is poor BAME representation in staff generally. In addition, there are few 'out' LGBTQ+ women in senior positions. In recent years, a 'promotion roadshow' has been delivered which has shown great success with increasing transparency in processes for career progression and understanding of how these systems work. These have benefitted both women and men.

The general feeling is that the University supports women across faculties and directorates to participate in the national [Aurora](#) initiative for women in higher education, with connection to the internal network of Aurora alumnae at Oxford Brookes. There is also in-house mentoring support. Mentoring for career progression is, therefore, identified to be available by OBU staff, although several interviewees confirmed that general understanding and knowledge about the in-house mentoring programme is "not as good as it could be: [because we] don't have the interventions in place". Therefore, take-up is not as high as it should be. Mentoring is felt to be particularly important for women. One leader discussed his involvement as a mentor, stating that he had initially felt that gender equality "is a subject by women, for women". However, he discussed this with senior colleagues who argued differently and then "came on board and now is on 3rd cohort mentoring women, as some women prefer a man as a mentor and though that's uncomfortable for some, it's what they want because 'that's where the power lies'".

People who were interviewed at OBU indicate that the institution also has a lack of clear, visible roles of successful women in leadership positions for aspiring, young women entering academia (particularly clarifying is the sentence: You can't be what you can't see).

The observation that women are well-represented at senior levels was in respect of both women professors and in the most senior leadership positions. In some faculties, there is a near equal split between professorial men and women. As data in the Institutional Report also reveals, however, women are over-represented in lower grades (particularly grade 6 which is dominated by administrative positions). This suggests that there are issues related to women's access to leadership and decision-making positions which may have implications for the 'pipeline'. Women are also over-represented in terms of part-time work, and this was acknowledged as being a potential constraint to career progression for some roles which are less suited to part-time work. A stigma around part-timedness, in that people believe senior roles cannot be part-time, was also felt to be widespread in managerial attitudes and part of the prevailing culture of the organisation. However, some argued that senior roles can successfully be carried out on a part-time basis, though needs some flexibility in those roles.

In addition, at faculty level some areas show a drop-off of women at levels leading into professorship, for example at reader level in humanities and social sciences. Other areas are entirely dominated by one gender, for example, mechanical engineering by men and nursing by women. It was also argued that there is a widespread expectation for women at a senior level

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“to be superhuman and selfless in some way”. Expectations on women to fulfil these roles were felt to be based on stereotypes which need to be challenged by the institution.

Finally, difficulties in returning to a research career following breaks for pregnancy, maternity and childcare/other caring responsibilities were seen to be an obstacle to women’s progression. One factor which was seen as helping with this is the existence of group coaching and informal mentors which has been put in place.

2.4. SU

Sabancı University also faces gender imbalance, both in some faculties’ bodies as well as in the highest decision-making, being the widest imbalance in the latter. If we attend to statistics, at University level, in all the bodies with the exception of the Director’s level, the presence of women is less than 40 per cent.

All interviews started by asking what interviewees think has been the role of gender in their career choice and paths, or whether they think it has a role at all. They were all pleasantly surprised by the question, indicated that this was not something they had thought about, or had to think about before, and as one interviewee expressed, the very fact that he did not have to think about this is quite telling in terms of the role of gender in shaping one’s career.

All interviewed leaders have positive and affirmative perspectives towards women’s role in society and academic life, and gender equality in general. Their sensitivity to issues regarding gender equality/inequality in society and work life stems from family backgrounds, i.e. growing up in egalitarian families with both parents working, academic backgrounds, i.e. receiving a high school education that embraced values such as inclusion and anti-discrimination. Having strong women as role models, including mothers, sisters, friends and colleagues was also mentioned in the interviews.

They all agree that there are obstacles to women’s career advancement in any sector in general, however, these obstacles do not exist at Sabancı University. It is possible to say that all interviewees contend that Sabancı University, as a private university in Istanbul with a strong academic track record and international prominence, has to be set aside from the rest of Turkey. Although leaders identify barriers to women’s advancement in their careers such as glass ceilings, access to leadership positions and others, they do not believe that such barriers exist at SU. They describe SU as a privileged environment. Many interviewees believe that Sabancı University has a “culture of equality,” and a background of talking about gender issues.

The fact that currently, all higher administrators are men with the exception of one woman dean is interpreted as a coincidence by all interviewees. They explained that the picture was different a few years ago, and the fact that all vice presidents and two thirds of all deans are men today

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is only coincidental and that they were chosen because they do their jobs well. However, they all believe that it is important to have more women in decision-making committees, to improve the situation and to make sure that different perspectives are included.

The analysis concludes that potentially the biggest resistance to change will be directed towards any proposed affirmative action policies. Although no such policies currently exist at SU, even when they were not asked about their opinion about positive discrimination, almost all respondents mentioned it themselves and express a negative attitude towards it. Five out of six refer to the meritocracy discourse and express a binary opposition between merit and positive discrimination; two respondents have slightly open but quiet hesitant attitudes towards affirmative action.

However, some informal practices are being carried out in the appointment processes, such as making sure that all committees in the Research and Graduate Policies Directorate have women.

SU also identified several informal factors limiting selection for management bodies and committees:

- Even distribution of the workload: assuring that is not the same people the ones that take part in all the commissions or management activities.
- Preference for Turkish-speaking candidates: unconsciously, there is a preference to Turkish speakers, as they state the conversation in the bodies are more fluid.

Decision-making processes are seen as not so transparent and inclusive, particularly due to the fact that the selection criteria are not public.

Finally, the analysis shows that while the leaders can identify areas for improvement regarding gender equality, or become aware of them during the course of the interview, only two out of the six interviewees used active language and identified themselves as change makers.

2.5. ETAg

ETAg also experiences gender imbalances in women representation in top positions, an issue which is currently addressed due to a personal boost of the Director General of ETAg to the appointment of women in that bodies that are more underrepresented.

The interviewees were asked about their general perception about gender equality in Estonia, with similar answers: they believe that we should pay more attention to this topic, although some of them consider that it is not the most important problem.

Inside the organization, both of them perceived that the imbalance is different when talking about their own workforce or about the expert panels and evaluation committees. In the case of the workforce, men are the underrepresented gender. However, in the case of expert panels,

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women faced a big imbalance in the past, reaching parity only in their last composition. In any case, no active policy has been done to reach this parity, but it is a matter of growing consciousness in the whole scientific world and RPOs nominating more women for committees.

The ETAg, and the Estonian society as a whole, also displays a high resistance to quotas as a positive affirmative measure (in particular, it is said that Estonian society is not prepared for quotas). Linked to that resistance, several people interviewed have the perception that time will solve the situations of imbalance, due to the incorporation of women to the top positions in science (which is the pool of people from which the institution selects its members). Both believes that gender balance in committees brings positive outcomes due to the “natural differences” of men and women.

A Research Funding Organization can play an important role in fostering gender mainstreaming. In this sense, the introduction of gender aspects in all research proposals is perceived as difficult, in particular in STEM areas

A last thing noticed was the perception of a lack of training about unconscious biases regarding gender issues. However, people inside the institution do not see this topic as a priority, as they recognize that there are other high importance topics to talk about and limited resources to deal with all of them.

2.6. UDEUSTO

The Institutional Assessment at DEUSTO suggested paying attention to several issues regarding leadership and decision-making.

Exploring the perceptions the respondents have about the reasons underlying the unequal distribution of leadership positions according to gender, asking about possible obstacles or challenges that women may face in access to these positions. Some voices claim roundly that “women have more difficulties than men in accessing positions of leadership in the society, everywhere”. Other, usually masculine, state they don’t know “where the brake is” or claim that women “have equal opportunities”, as “the university seeks “that profiles that can better perform those purposes without taking gender into account”.

Nevertheless, addressing this issue, the respondents’ speeches often pointed out the workload and the time dedication that involve management positions, aspects that are in conflict with family roles socially attributed to women and with the values and codes internalised by these.

The tension between work and family demands is expressed with higher anxiety and challenge in women. Some of them point out that the difficulty of access to management positions lies in “the ongoing effort that needs to be done to keep the professional and personal life balance”. Their speeches help us understand how the internalised construction of femininity, linked to the care of the children and the family, in interaction with a labour structure designed on the basis

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of the masculine traditional experience (exempt from the social mandate to care, entirely available for the job), can mediate in the decisions of women with family responsibilities in the assumption of management positions. All this appears to come off the perception that women who surpass the “glass ceiling” are women with a more advanced age or with no reproductive responsibilities.

Another issue that emerges in the narratives is the disaffection or distance experienced by women toward leadership roles, they perceive and live it as something foreign to them. Once again, the positions and gender attributions shape, often in invisible ways, attitudes towards these positions. Thus, the femininity which is not built as leader can whip up fears and insecurities in decision-making about the access to these positions, which requires “emotional stability, baggage and support”.

The feeling of insecurity or inability to play the position, along with the lack of valuation or merit associated to the own position display - the so-called “Impostor syndrome” - synthesizes the contradiction between the traditional femininity construction (such as lower or secondary –“the unessential”–) and the leadership roles, traditionally male-dominated.

There are a number of statements that mention the incidence of “culture” or “tradition” as an obstacle to women inclusion in senior management positions. In particular, it points out the difficulty of a woman holding the Rector position, as the UDEUSTO is a Jesuit university (men religious order), which sets up a “glass ceiling” difficult to transfer, despite the –relatively recent– regulatory change that would allow a woman to occupy the position.

Beyond the assertions that women have the same opportunities, when executing the election of senior positions according to the self-worth, the narratives’ deepening elicits the rise of pitfalls of diverse nature that contribute to the “scissors-effect” detected in the quantitative part. Structural obstacles, such as the design of the leadership positions from a male perspective (traditionally exempt of reproductive responsibilities), are linked to symbolic walls, as the interiorisation of the construction of femininity as a caregiver and not as a leader, to what it is added the society’s and institution’s culture and inertia.

The collected speeches agree highlighting that, in recent years, changes in favour of equality opportunity and female leadership have occurred in the UDEUSTO.

However, the quota’s measure frequently awakens rejection attitudes and resistance among the people consulted, especially among men. Expressions like “I don’t share it at all”, “I don’t like them”, “I don’t really agree” are repeated in the speeches collected. Their arguments point out that the selection criteria should be the worth and the performance, as it may be counter-productive to generate, on the women who ascend, the feeling that they are “trophy wife” or “a quota”, or that she might pose problems when the reverse situation occurs in the future or in certain sectors. On top of this, the belief that equality will come as part of a natural process

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of social evolution, lead to the perception that the measure is not necessary. By contrast, several other discourses, despite expressing an initial opposition to the measure, claim that it may be a necessary tool against this inequality situation that exists in the management bodies of the university.

The mentoring and counselling of women elicits, in general, larger adhesions between people consulted.

Likewise, to overcome the structural conditions that hinder reconciliation and favour men to occupy senior positions at the university –and generically, in institutions of our environment– some discourses mark the need to rethink the management model of the institution and, in particular, the long working and inflexible schedules linked to these positions.

Regarding leadership models, the idea that women and men have “different sensitivities” and a “separated” leadership which can be “complementary” is frequently repeated in the stories of the people consulted. These also pointed that “there are common principles” and “there’s everything” in both collectives, in a manner that one cannot speak about “exclusive features”. Some people placed in the extremes noted that it is “another way of looking at” the face of those who, without denying the difference, suspect that this “will not have a great magnitude”.

Although the manifestations of the people consulted differ in their rotundity, they speak about a female leadership characterised by traits such as empathy, care, moodiness, patience, dialogue, and the more global vision, against a male leadership described as more task-oriented and dynamic steering.

Finally, despite the fact that the consulted people considered that the UDEUSTO, through its historical journey and religious link, had traditionally decided on male leaders, they support the inherent Ignatian leadership of this Jesuit institution promotes listening, dialogue and the care for people. Many voices link these characteristics to a stereotypically “more feminine”, “inclusive” leadership model. Furthermore, in general, there is a claim to be placed with ease in this leadership ideology, which tries to seek “a balance” between task orientation and people’s care.

3. Recommendations for GEPs

Once the different specificities and concerns raised in each institution have been addressed, in this section we aim to provide more general recommendations to inform the GEP design process specifically in the field of leadership and decision-making .

Based on the desk research of best practices that has been carried out in the context of WP5 and contained in Deliverable 5.1, we will provide recommendations taking into consideration the four areas of intervention identified: actions related with trainings and leadership

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development; role-providing, coaching and mentoring; networking and knowledge sharing; and specific funding schemes. In order to design specific actions that are feasible to include in GEPs, we will try to avoid recommendations related to funding schemes, as most of the institutions have not the required financial autonomy to set up this kind of programmes.

3.1. Common action I: Networking and Knowledge sharing at consortium-level

Being in the core of the project, one of the main aims of GEARING-Roles Project is to provide inter-institutional support and support in the process of implementing GEPs and the actions arising from them. Therefore, we strongly recommend developing a networking strategy between all the GEP implementing partners in the leadership field. In particular, we should try to look for specific moments during the life of the project to bring leaders of all the institutions together in to share their main progresses and strategies towards integrating the gender perspective in the management processes.

We believe the institutional pairing need to serve to this purpose, as well as to open communication channels among leaders of the different organizations. In these sessions, apart from the workshops about leadership and decision-making (see Deliverable 5.4. for a detailed description), several informal spaces are allocated, in which the networking between the participating leaders would be enhanced.

3.2. Common action II: Consortium-level trainings

Apart from the networking events, we believe that, for any structural change process to be successful, it is vital to give change- makers the tools to deal with it. In this sense, several formative activities are planned at a consortium level. This activities would target different groups at GEP implementers: current members of the management bodies; members of the core groups of the project; current and potential female leaders; and general public with interest about the development of gender structural change in higher education.

The specific set of activities that have been planned and delivered is contained in the Deliverable 5.4, which sets the objectives and content of each of them.

3.3. IGOT

IGOT needs firstly to make the top management leaders aware of the biases that may exist in decision-making processes. For that purpose, one recommendation is to have training sessions with them so they are able to identify that biases and re-shape the appointment processes taking into consideration gender issues.

Then, working with women it is also needed. First, to identify what factors make some women decline top positions. And, once these factors are identified, coaching and mentorship

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interventions are suitable for removing the barriers women may encounter in this processes of postulating themselves to become leaders.

3.4. UL

At UL, one of the main problems has to do with the struggle between meritocracy and gender-balance criteria. In order to deal with this issue, it is necessary to work with HR department in order to develop clear decision-making processes which integrates both aspects, as they are compatible. In this process, awareness raising activities with existing bodies are also needed, as they are the ones that has to give support to HR in the implementation of the new processes (which will also reinforce the changes in process and the new criteria).

The other recommendation has to do with the perception of a leadership position as a WLB problem and workload. Here, we have to bring together HR and women senior academics to develop some activity to co-create a specific WLB programme for leaders, taking into consideration the additional responsibility these positions imply.

3.5. OBU

It would be interesting to develop a Role-Providing scheme at OBU, so that they can give voice to successful women in high academic and management positions within the university. In this sense, it would be interesting that some tool AcademiaNet (see D5.1 for further information) could be fed with information related to OBU personnel, so that it can be an easy, public way of identifying influential women and put them in touch with junior women aiming to reach high positions in the future.

3.6. SU

As stated in UL section, SU has to develop clear and transparent criteria for the appointment of candidates to managerial positions. Therefore, we need to involve HR and existing committees and leaders to shape this processes and communicate them to the academic community.

As the leaders and senior academics have some concerns regarding the different styles of men and women in leadership, it will be worth to have sessions with them and experts in leadership in order to clarify concepts, talk about the differences (if any) in leadership of men and women at SU.

3.7. ETAg

The situation of ETAg is quite different from the other GEP implementing partners due to its status of RFO instead of being a performing organization. But, in any case, the main issue that faces is related with the awareness raising and training leaders in the benefits of having more balanced organizations, so they can start looking at it as a structural problem rather than an external factor that would be solved without intervention.

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Furthermore, they also identified the lack of training regarding biases, so some specific programme in the field needs to be tailored.

3.8. UDEUSTO

UDEUSTO needs to start by raising awareness of the differences in the women access to management positions at university. Therefore, specific trainings with the Board of Directors are recommended, so that they could be aware of the different biases decision-making processes could have. One example of this type of actions is the AKKA Programme.

The university also has to work with women, in several ways. First off, they have to develop programmes to strengthen the abilities of women who are currently in top positions and their potential within the bodies they belong to.

Besides, it is needed to identify potential candidates for leadership positions and diversification of profiles, and create a specific programme mixing training actions and mentorship, to give them the necessary tools and attitudes to achieve higher positions in the near future.

Finally, to deal with the WLB issues for leaders, it would be interesting to give HR Department with suggestions to redesigning the burden of leadership tasks (meeting schedules, redistribution of other tasks) and make the reconciliation of leaders possible. In other words, to assess and propose improvements of the leadership model of the institution.

The following table summarizes all the recommendations to include in GEPs, providing some examples of tools or instruments that could serve as inspiration.

ACTIONS	PARTNER BENEFITED	TOOLS/INSTRUMENTS
Network strategy / Networking among leaders	All	GEARING Roles Institutional Pairing Events
Capacity building for change-makers	All	D5.4
Raising awareness on biases	All	Trainings AKKA (D5.1)
Supporting women to enrolling leadership positions	IGOT, UDEUSTO	Coaching Mentoring AKADEME (D5.1)
Meritocracy vs gender equality	OBU, UL	AcademiaNet (D5.1) BALANSE (D5.1)

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Redefine the burdens of leadership (WLB and workload)	UL, UDEUSTO	Reflection groups on each institution for cultural change: Higher Education Leadership Programs for Women.HERS (D5.1)
Give visibility to successful women in high academic and management positions	OBU	Role-providing scheme AcademiaNet initiative (D5.1)
Develop clear and transparent criteria for the appointment of candidates to managerial positions	UL, SU	Gender Initiative for Excellence – GENIE (D5.1) Action Plan for Improving the Gender Balance in Academic Positions (D5.1)

3. Final Remarks

In this report, we have pretended to give GEP implementers with some recommendations so that they could consider feeding their GEPs with them in the leadership and decision-making area together with recommendations of tools and resources that could help, including relevant project activities and results.

In doing so, several common challenges have been identified, most of them dealing with the so-called equality mirage (i.e. a perception that gender equality is no longer a problem and is currently achieved or will be achieved by the normal course of events) and meritocracy discourse in the appointment of new leaders.

From the existing practices, the most relevant ones for the situation and progress of each GEPI have been selected. Plus, two consortium-level activities have been planned in order to complement each GEPI's Action Plan: the development of good connections among partners to facilitate the exchange of experiences; and the development of a common training programme for different groups. This programme will give individuals the necessary elements to first understand and second deal with the different elements involved in a process of structural change in the field of leadership: resistances, biases and the justification of the need to change, among others.

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